

**This is the author's own translation of the following
original French language publication:**

Collins Mark, « “Les gros poissons se cachent”. Frictions entre conceptions du vivant marin sur l'île de Lavongai (Papouasie-Nouvelle-Guinée) », *Journal de la Société des Océanistes*, 2021/2 (n° 153), p. 337-352. DOI : 10.4000/jso.13344. URL : <https://www-caim-info.lama.univ-amu.fr/revue-journal-de-la-societe-des-oceanistes-2021-2-page-337.htm>

‘The big fish hide’. Frictions between perceptions of marine life on Lavongai Island (Papua New Guinea)

by

Mark Collins*

Abstract

On the shores of Lavongai Island (also known as New Hanover), in the Bismarck archipelago of Papua New Guinea, interactions are taking place between various perceptions of marine life, in the context of climate change and coastal ecosystem degradation. The inhabitants of the island say that big fish are now hiding. They explain this by a lack of respect towards the reefs shown by some people, who disregard traditional social norms. Exogenous considerations on these matters also reach the island, highlighting the dangers of using toxic plants to catch fish, and the risks of Malthusian over-fishing. The two environmental NGOs that voice such concerns encourage locals to create marine protected areas. Based on three months of ethnographic fieldwork conducted in late 2019, this article focuses on the ‘frictions’ between these different points of view, and analyses how such frictions reconfigure or revalue various aspects of knowledge.

KEYWORDS: human-animal relations, fisheries, marine conservation, Lavongai (New Hanover), Papua New Guinea

Introduction: knowledge and points of view regarding fish

This article is about relations between humans and marine animals, and is concerned with reconfigurations and revaluations of knowledge on the shores of Lavongai island, in Papua New Guinea (PNG). First, some theoretical context will be needed in order to frame this discussion.

Interactions between human societies and marine life have, for almost a century now, been the topic of some attention in Oceanian anthropology (see, among others: Firth, 1931; Johannes, 1981; Dye, 1983; Blanchet, 1999; Hviding, 2003a; Leblic, 2008; Ono, 2010; Schneider, 2013; Calandra, 2018), in particular in the *Journal de la Société des Océanistes* (see n° 72-73, and its introduction: Bataille-Benguigui, 1981). The ecological knowledge of Oceanian populations, under the various denominations of ‘indigenous’ or ‘traditional ecological knowledge’ (Roué, 2012), has also been the focus of a considerable body of literature (see for example: Inglis, 1993; Williams and Baines, 1993; Menzies, 2006; Butler *et al.*, 2012; Macintyre and Foale, 2013; Travési, 2020). More recently, various scholars have focussed on the issues brought about in Pacific-island locations by encounters between so-called environmental non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and local populations, when the former carry out conservation actions, both on land (see in particular: Helden, 2001; West, 2006) and at sea (Foale, 2002; Hviding, 2003b; Foale and Manele, 2004; Gaspar and Bambridge, 2008; Foale *et al.*, 2011; Leblic and Cornier, 2018; Fache and Pauwels, 2020).

The present discussion is articulated from the intersection of those three topics: interactions between humans and marine life, ecological knowledge, and issues arising in the context of environmental NGOs’ actions. Moreover, it is framed in the more general context of global anthropogenic climate change, ecosystem degradation, and massive biodiversity loss (Díaz *et al.*, 2019). The re-

* *Doctoral student in anthropology, Aix Marseille Univ, CNRS, EHESS, CREDO, Marseille, France
mark.collins@univ-amu.fr

sponsibility that each human society bears in causing these changes varies greatly, and there is no consensus regarding appropriate ways to respond to it (see: Rudiak-Gould, 2015; Glowczewski and Laurens, 2018). Here, one of the main themes is brought about as a consequence of this absence of a consensus. In the book *Friction: an ethnography of global connection*, American anthropologist Anna L. Tsing notes how climate change, ecosystem degradation, and loss of biodiversity have caused a multiplication of encounters between different points of view regarding life (Tsing, 2005: 101-102). Indeed, narratives depicting the negative character of these phenomena have spread far and wide around the globe, insisting on the dangerous nature of the current changed—for mankind, but also, more generally, for the biosphere—and on the need for action if the effects are to be limited, in order to adapt to them, or to prevent them altogether. Environmental NGOs are among the prime creators and disseminators of such narratives (see Doyle, 2009). They carry out actions in places and within societies that can be very different from those their members originate from, and bring a point of view on these topics which is situated, and thus meets that of the ‘locals’. Anna Tsing writes that: ‘Cultures are continually co-produced in the interactions [she] call “friction”: the awkward, unequal, unstable, and creative qualities of interconnection across difference’ (Tsing, 2005: 4). She also writes that such ‘friction’ gives new value to, and recomposes new forms of knowledge, in particular by virtue of what she terms ‘tentative and contingent collaborations among disparate knowledge seekers and their disparate forms of knowledge’ (Tsing, 2005: 89). Such collaborations, A. Tsing goes on:

‘can turn incompatible facts and observations into compatible ones. Just as tiny convergences in incompatible testimonies at a criminal trial can establish a line of truth, the founding lines through which we learn to recognize Nature are often established in convergent opinions. Convergences offer legitimacy and charisma to nascent categories. They offer bridges over unrecognizable difference. Convincing universals must be able to travel with at least some facility in the world, and this requires negotiations across incompatible difference. Upon occasion, these give rise to collaboratively agreed upon Natural objects. The unfamiliar becomes the familiar through this process, and generalization can occur.’ (Tsing, 2005: 89)

This article aims to analyse such ‘tentative and contingent collaborations’, between a population of gardeners and fishermen, and two environmental NGOs that focus on marine conservation. This article is based on three months of ethnographic fieldwork carried out on Lavongai¹, an island in the Bismarck archipelago, in the New Ireland Province of PNG (see MAP 1). By means of this ethnographic example, I wish to shed some light on the more general question: how is knowledge recomposed and given new value during interactions between multiple perspectives regarding marine life? Said in another way: as various points of view on marine-dwelling beings meet, which new forms of knowledge appear, how are they linked to pre-existing elements of knowledge from one, or the other of the several epistemologies of the people involved? I will start by describing in more detail the methods used during the enquiry, and the people involved. Then, I will describe, by using an example, the relations between the inhabitants of the Lavongai coast and marine animals. Finally, I will go in detail into three forms of ‘friction’ that I observed between the perspectives of the Lavongai, and those of the two NGOs, and I will analyse their consequence on the knowledge of those involved.

1 The name is also sometimes spelled Lovongai or Lovangai. The island is also known under its colonial toponym: New Hannover.

MAP 1 – Situation of Lavongai in Western Oceania and location of places referred to herein. Map data from Open Street Map (<https://openstreetmap.org>). By Mark Collins, created in QGIS (<https://qgis.org>).

Methodology and parties involved

The island of Lavongai is approximately 30 km north to south, and 50 km east to west. It is mountainous (rising up to almost 900 m altitude) and surrounded by coral reefs. The population of approximately 30 000 (UNOCHA and PNG NSO, 2012)² lives mainly on the coast (see MAP 2) in relatively spread out villages and hamlets. Two anthropologists: Dorothy Billings (1969, 1972, 2002) and Jason Roberts (2019a, 2019b) have carried out extended periods of fieldwork there, but neither one focussed on maritime topics.

Between September and December 2019, in the context of a masters degree in anthropology, I carried out ethnographic fieldwork on the southern coast of the island, in the village of Metevoe (see MAP 1) where about 500 people live. I carried out interviews in Tok Pisin, one of PNG’s official languages, which I learned during my stay. In collaboration with several interpreters—in particular Laimen Beling, my host in Metevoe—we recorded and transcribed songs, conversations and various forms of discourse in Tungak³, the vernacular language spoken around the island, in which I also

2 Nationwide census are carried out every ten years in PNG. The one that was supposed to take place in 2021 has been postponed until 2024 because of the Covid-19 pandemic (PNG NSO, 2021). The reliability of the 2011 census has been questioned (Bourke and Allen, 2021) and these figures are therefore indicative only.

3 Tungak or Tungag is an Austronesian language for which no dictionary yet has been published. Several linguistic publications have been made relating to the language (Stamm, 1988; Fast, 1990) including a PhD thesis on Tungak’s spatial language, that includes a detailed and precise grammar, by a linguist who grew up on the island: Karin Fast (2015); see also <https://glottolog.org/resource/languoid/id/tung1290>.

learned basic communication. Moreover, the inhabitants of Metevoe and I worked together in order to produce a marine ethnobiological inventory, which contains terminology and local knowledge regarding beings living in or around the sea and coast, descriptions of their aspect, behaviour, habitat, their uses or dangers.

MAP2 – Representation of the number of inhabitants and of languages spoken on the island of Lavongai and neighbouring islets. Map data from Open Street Map (<https://openstreetmap.org>); demographic data from the United Nations Bureau for the Coordination of Humanitarian affairs, based on the latest available census, carried out in 2011 by the National Statistical Office of PNG (<https://perma.cc/7LJV-YC5D>); linguistic data from the Summer Institute of Linguistics (<https://pnglanguages.sil.org>). By Mark Collins, created in QGIS (<https://qgis.org>).

The inhabitants of Lavongai are⁴, above all, tuber growers. In their swidden gardens they produce two types of aracea: taro (*Colocasia esculenta*) and macabo (*Xanthosoma sagittifolium*), sweet potatoes (*Ipomoea batatas*), bananas (*Musa spp.*), and manioc (*Manihot esculenta*) as well as, more rarely, yams (*Dioscorea alata* and *Dioscorea esculenta*). They also use sagos (*Metroxylon sagu*) to build their houses and produce sago, a starchy flour, from the plant's core. They raise pigs and chickens. Pig meat is reserved for ceremonial exchanges that takes place mostly during the multi-year funeral cycle. Meat from chickens is only seldom eaten, as are chicken's eggs. The Lavongai also hunt, in the forest, using bamboo spears with steel tips and sometimes with the assistance of dogs. Thus, they catch 'wild' pigs, cuscus (*Phalanger spp.*) and wallabies (*Thylogale spp.*) and eat their meat.

4 My writing in the 'ethnographic present tense' refers to the time of my visit to Lavongai. It does not mean to suggest any form of temporal generalisation, not that the people or facts described are in any way 'stuck' in any moment of their history.

Their sustenance is therefore mostly guaranteed by the plants they cultivate. Nevertheless, the Lavongai that live near the shore fish on a daily basis, and collect invertebrates from the reefs and coastal waters, and the sea is even their prime source of protein. Fishing activities are practised by all: men, women and children, but in differing ways. Men fish with hooks and lines from single-hulled dugout outrigger canoes, either by weighting a line down to the sea floor or by dragging it behind the canoe, and they also dive in order to spear fish with bamboo and steel spears or with the occasional home made spear-gun. Women fish by standing on the reef with a non weighted line and hook, or collect invertebrates. Children mostly use the same techniques as women⁵.

Two NGOs are present in the area. The first, called Ailan Awareness⁶, was founded in 1993 by three men from Lavongai: two brothers, John and Bernard Miller Aini, and Michael Ladi (Aini and West, 2013). Paige West, an American anthropologist, also has a very important involvement in the organisation (West and Aini, 2021: 70). Nowadays, Ailan Awareness is mainly managed by John Aini, and is active in various locations throughout the region, in particular on Lavongai island, where it promotes durable use and management of marine resources. It is based in Kaslock, about 20 km from Kavieng on the island of New Ireland (see MAP 1)⁷. The NGO has limited financial capabilities, that are made up mostly of donations made by an anonymous international donor. Some Ailan Awareness members also receives, on occasion, receive allowances from another, international, NGO: the Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS)⁸, when the two carry out joined operations.

This second NGO, WCS, is based in New York. It has a regional Melanesian section that is seated in Suva in Fiji, a PNG head office in Goroka, and, since the early 2000s, has had a regional office in Kavieng. Among the permanent employees of the latter office, one is a British ‘expat’, who, for this work, has been living in Kavieng for several years, the others are from elsewhere in PNG. Some Lavongai are at times employed by the NGO to carry out temporary work when activities are organised on the island. I observed WCS employees preparing an awareness ‘tour’, and during several such awareness presentations with various communities. The NGO enjoys a rather considerable budget (336 millions US dollars income in 2018), which is largely made up of donor contributions (WCS, 2019: 47).

Members of both NGOs regularly travel to Lavongai to meet with inhabitants and promote durable forms of management of marine resources. In the remainder of this article, I will therefore be referring to three perspectives: that of the inhabitants, that of Ailan Awareness, and that of WCS. Each one of these wholes is a generalisation of a plurality of individual considerations that can vary through time and within each group. I do not purport here to speak ‘for’ the Lavongai, nor either of the two NGOs; the presentation I make of each perspective attempts to be as faithful as possible, but I alone am responsible for it. With this limitation in mind, I will now begin by describing the relations the Lavongai have with marine animals, by means of an example: a species of fish called *riranga*.

Lavongai relations to marine life: *riranga* as an example

Lavongai knowledge regarding marine life is of considerable breadth and depth, as is readily demonstrated by the size of the marine ethnobiological inventory we drew up in just a few months with a handful of inhabitants from Metevoe. This contains 245 entries, of which 175 fish, 48 inver-

5 During my fieldwork, the context was that of a strong separation of activities between the sexes. The fact that I am a man therefore means that I observed men’s actions far more than I did women’s. On all levels of social activity, I only had limited access to women’s discourse or practices.

6 The word *ailan* means ‘island’ in Tok Pisin (see <https://ailanawareness.wordpress.com/>).

7 During my fieldwork, I also stayed at the Ranguwa Solwara Skul (Ranguwa marine school, in Tok Pisin), at Kaslock, where Ailan Awareness is based, on the suggestion of Paige West and generously hosted by John Aini.

8 See the website of the PNG branch of WCS (<https://png.wcs.org/>).

tebrates, four plants, six birds, five corals, five turtles, the marine crocodile, dolphin, whale and dugong⁹. This knowledge is valued, transmitted from generation to generation, and used on a daily basis. It is also constantly evolving, as much under influences and advice from outside sources, as it is in reaction to changes the Lavongai perceive in their environment.

Indeed, the fact that climate change (*klimat senis* in Tok Pisin) is threatening Lavongai is apparent for them. The people I spoke to in Metevoe about this topic tie it into what they clearly perceive to be a receding coastline, which they say is caused by the rising sea level (see PHOTO 1); about thirty years ago, houses apparently stood where waves now lap over sand. The inhabitants notice other changes occurring in their environment, regarding the fauna: fish are said to no longer be as big as they used to. People say the larger fish *chose* not to show themselves: ‘before, we used to catch big fish in our passes. Now, these big fish hide, they don't come out any more’ (Laimen Beling, 45 year old man, Metevoe, 19/10/2019¹⁰). The state of various areas of the reef is also compared and commented on: such a part is said to be ‘beautiful, with many colours’, such another to be ‘dead, because it has no more colour’ (Julius Otis, 38 year old man, Metevoe, 25/09/2019).

9 These figures may be compared, for example, to the 139 fish names and 62 names of other marine species obtained in three months in the Jorio region on the island of Vella Lavalla in the Solomon Islands by no less than 8 researchers (Cohen *et al.*, 2014); or the 200 fish names that a group of Vula'a from the village of Irupara, in PNG's Central Province collected (Van Heekeren, 2017: 7).

10 The people who are named here agreed to be referred to in my future work.

PHOTO 1 – On the beach of Metevoe, this tree was uprooted during a storm. For the inhabitants, such changes on their shores are signs of climate change. By Mark Collins, Metevoe, 22/10/2019.

Can the consequences of climate change be seen ‘with the naked eye’? That is a question which remains largely unanswered, and has complex political implications (see in particular: Rudiak-Gould, 2013; or for a more local approach in the Cook Islands: Glory, 2019; and in Vanuatu: Pascht, 2019). In any case, the Lavongai also state what they see as the immediate causes of these changes: they are said to be brought about by the inappropriate behaviour of some of the island’s inhabitants, those who don’t have the right ways towards the marine environment, and neglect traditional social injunctions in this domain. In the words of my interlocutors, such individuals ‘don’t have respect’, a sentence I heard many times about the ways of ‘some people’ towards the sea (these ways, and people usually remained unspecified). Such discourse therefore highlights a set of prescribed behaviours that should be adopted in order for marine life to ‘thrive’, which I will now explain by using an example.

The Lavongai have a particular relationship with a fish called *riranga*¹¹. This term refers to one of six named stages of development for what is considered to be one animal at various periods of maturity (from smallest to largest: *vunep*, *kisimerung*, *manikvalsilang*, *riranga*, *ra* and *lenge*). At the *riranga* stage, they are juveniles, fine transparent filaments of approximately one to two centimetres. Their particularity is that they aggregate in great numbers near the shores, before swimming upstream in various rivers¹². When they are present, it is very easy to capture *riranga* (see PHOTO 2). Men and women then fish for them together, and with very little effort bring home large quantities.

11 In Tok Pisin, these fish are called *ainanga*. Many Oceanian languages include cognates of this term; such is the case of *inanga* in New-Zealand Maori for example (see the webpage of the Department of Conservation about *inanga*: <https://perma.cc/4K3F-3P8V>).

12 A fish that has such behaviour, migrating between sea and river is said to be ‘amphidromous’. Visual identification of *riranga* is impossible, even for the marine biologists I asked, and only genetic analysis might make it possible to determine the exact species involved here. In New Zealand, *inanga* refers to *Galaxias maculatus*, but this species is not present in tropical waters. The number of amphidromous fish in the region is however quite low, and on Lavongai *riranga* might therefore be identified as *Eleotris spp.* or *Giuris spp.*

PHOTO 2 – Two men stand on the reef flat, in Metevoe bay, and capture *riranga* with a mosquito net, at nightfall. The net is between them, just below the surface of the water. In the distance, the photo also shows other men who are fishing *riranga* with the help of young men in canoes, who are looking out for the rustling the fish cause when they swim just under the surface. By Mark Collins, Metevoe, 09/10/2019.

The inhabitants of the Lavongai coast explain that these juvenile fish come from the sea to aggregate near the shores and estuaries, where they stay for variable amounts of time before swimming up river and becoming adults. In order to maximise the amount of time *riranga* spend aggregating near the shore, prescriptions and prohibitions are outlined.

First of all, no toxic substances should be placed in the water either, and fishing with deris root¹³ in particular is forbidden. Indeed, this is considered damageable for marine life, since it ‘kills everything, even small fish’, as Bruce once told me, adding with irony and disapproval:

‘those who fish with deris root only catch small fish that are full of bones. Do we eat fish, or do we eat bones?’ (Bruce, approx. 60 year old man, Metevoe, 12/10/2019.)

Moreover, pregnant women, or women who have their periods, as well as the husbands of these women, shouldn’t go into the sea, nor even on the shore. Such prohibitions, that relate to the danger

13 Such fishing techniques use ichthyotoxic substances to kill or immobilise fish. They are officially prohibited in PNG (Papua New Guinea, 1998: 94), but are in fact used widely in the area, be it inland on New Guinea island (Bonne-mère, 1996: 137), on the shores of the Solomon islands (Rickard and Cox, 1986) or in New Caledonia (Leblic, 1995). Several plants can be used to this effect; at Metevoe, the one that is the most often used is called *tua* (*bunbun* in Tok Pisin, *Derris* spp.), a word that is cognate of *tuba* which refers to such plants in several oceanic languages (see in New Caledonia, Leblic, 1995: 220, note 6; in Fiji: Nolet, 2018: §40). They contain rotenone, a substance highly toxic to fish.

that female bodily substances are thought to represent in the context of fishing, exist elsewhere in Oceania (in Tongan shark fishing see: Bataille-Benguigui, 1986: 409-410; in New Caledonia: Leblanc, 2008: 233).

Besides these prohibitions, a prescription must be followed in order to cause *riranga* to aggregate: the catch must be shared widely. The amount of fish obtained in a relatively short amount of time implies a type of preservation: women place *riranga* in leaf envelopes before cooking them in the *imun*, an oven made from river stones, which produces packets of a salty tasteful paste that keeps well. This can then be sprinkled into dishes and is on occasion sold at a price that might seem considerable, given how easy the fish are to catch¹⁴. Nevertheless, a man would never think to give all his catch to his wife in order for her to cook it in the oven, preserve it then sell it. Indeed, if the good graces of *riranga* are to be obtained, then all the village's inhabitants must first eat some boiled *riranga*. Once all have had a share, women will start to cook it in the oven. It is a well established fact that 'in Melanesia, [...] the sharing of food is the most fundamental form of sociality' (Lemonnier, 2009: 242, own translation; see also, for example, Dousset, 2016, 2018). Beyond the renewed observation of this fact, the case of *riranga* is remarkable because the Lavongai are, in this case, stating the importance of sharing food by projecting the consequences of their actions onto the behaviour of the sea animal.

These two imperatives—keeping pollution away, and sharing the catch—make up the backbone of the respect owed to *riranga*. This example illustrates in more general terms the importance of such respect in relations the Lavongai have with all living marine beings. The use of such a term, 'respect', might seem surprising since these relations are, by and large, made up of predation. However, such close ties between predation and respect have been underlined in much ethnographic literature, in particular from the Amazon (Descola, 2005: 542-543; Viveiros de Castro, 2012: 22-23), but also in Oceania. Marie-Claire Bataille-Benguigui writes that in Tonga:

'fishing techniques are gentle and must align with the respect and consideration afforded to the fish. [...] The aim of fishing is not to obtain high yields, but to respect the fish and prohibitions.' (Bataille-Benguigui, 1986: 410, own translation)

The Lavongai's perspective regarding marine life therefore leaves a lot of room for the fish's intentionality and agency: the animals decide—according to local discourse—to come near the shore or not to, to aggregate or not to, to bite a hook, or not to. This agency afforded to prey-animals has often been observed by ethnographers in societies where hunting plays an important role (see in the circumpolar area: Brightman, 2002; Nadasdy, 2007; Ingold, 2012; regarding fishing for the Inuit: Todd, 2015). Considering that non-human animals have agency is also a fact that has been observed in many Oceanian societies, although it has been written about less extensively (see nevertheless, regarding bonito in the Solomon Islands: Davenport, 1980, 1990; sharks in Tonga: Bataille-Benguigui, 1988; bonito in Tonga: Leslie, 2005; sea birds and fish in Kiribati: Di Piazza, 2005).

Giving consideration to Lavongai's coastal inhabitants' relations with marine animals therefore mostly highlights social preoccupations, and shows how important these beings' agency is to the people involved, and the high degree of respect they afford them. What happens when friction occurs between such a point of view regarding these beings and others?

14 A pack of oven-cooked *riranga* of approximately 300 g was sold for ten kina in 2019. The kina is PNG's official currency. Ten kina were equivalent to about 3 € in late 2019 and could be used to buy two 1 kg pack of rice, or twenty medium-sized fishing hooks.

From friction to recomposition of knowledge

Vala and marine protected areas

What is *vala* on Lavongai? The answer to this question depends quite heavily on who the interlocutor is. Karin Fast, a linguist whose doctoral thesis is about spatial language in Tungak, translates this term by ‘marker’ (Fast, 2015: 225).

This word is used by some fishermen who have special ritual knowledge that they describe as allowing them to *malira* (‘charm’, ‘use love magic on’) fish, which could be rendered generally by the expression ‘propitiatory rituals for fishing’¹⁵. Such rituals start with rigorous preparation of the fisherman and the surroundings. He must avoid his wife and not be seen by any women. He must fast, *alal* (literally ‘abstinence’), a practice that varies in its application, but which is closely tied to avoidance of fresh water: he cannot drink, root vegetables must be roasted on a fire rather than boiled¹⁶, and sago—a food which is processed using large quantities of water—is forbidden. He must also clear the reef flat of all pollution. Two scholars who originate from Lavongai, Tukul W. Kaiku and Patrick K. Kaiku, describe such rituals in an article under the name ‘sardine farming’, and state that the fisherman must first of all remove from the shore:

‘man-made impurities or any natural unclean substance (for example, rotting carcasses of a dead animal). [...] notorious pollutions that confront [him] are coconut husks (*peniniu*), used food parcel leaves (*ingere i-fok*), human excrement (*ita*), blood from menstruating females and common household rubbish (*mung*) that have been dumped into the sea” (Kaiku and Kaiku, 2008: 63).

The rituals involve secret songs, and preparing various plant materials, making a *kurip* out of them (a bundle or basket), then placing them under a *ngoto* (a pile of stones), on the reef flat. The plants that are used are each associated with a specific fish: *kulava* (a trevaly, *Carax sp.*), *konemekul* (narrow barred Spanish mackerel, *Scomberomorus commerson*), *las* (rainbow runner, *Elagatis bipinnulata*), *malus* (jacks, *Decapterus spp.*) or *olo* (mojarras, *Gerres spp.*)—among others. These songs call on the powers of specific *anit*, a category of ‘supernatural beings’, spirits of deceased ancestors who have passed their ritual knowledge on to the practitioner and give it its efficacy, and at times also on intercessor marine birds such as *vokol* (the Pacific reef heron, *Egretta sacra*) or *kanai* (terns, *Sternidae* family). Different aims might be sought by each song: to call fish near the beach, to make them less ‘wild’, easier to approach, or to ‘feed’ them so they will stay on the reef. In order to show where the ritual has taken place, the practitioner then places a *vala* into the *ngoto*: a stick of wood, approximately two to three metres high, with a few leaves still on it, and at times with *vang* attached (a plant, also called *erege*, a cordyline, *Cordyline fruticosa*). This signals to all that ritual work has been carried out in this location, and to stay away from it.

The same word, *vala*, is used by Ailan Awareness. The NGO promotes the use of a local traditional form of marine protected area, called *vala*, as John Aini, co-founder of the NGO, explained to me during an interview (8/09/2019, Kaselok), and in the public communications he gave during awareness sessions. In a short film that was shot with the collaboration of Ailan Awareness about this practice, *Vala North* (Gordon, 2019), *vala* is said to:

- 15 In Metevoe, I met five men who practised such rituals, and at Kaselok in New Ireland, I met a sixth, who was from the village of Lavongai. One man in Metevoe, and the latter at Kaselok agreed to record several songs and together we translated them into Tok Pisin, then English. The ritual practices are shrouded in considerable secrecy, and are coveted to a degree, which is why I do not name the people involved here, and will give only an outline of what the rituals consist of.
- 16 Cooking in boiling water is used on a daily basis by women, but only rarely by men, who prefer to roast tubers in a fire. Avoiding this form of cooking could therefore be related to the avoidance of one’s wife and other women.

‘involve a stick placed on the area in question as a symbol of restriction to stop any activity from occurring in that particular area¹⁷.’

This practice is akin to others observed around Oceania, in particular off the coasts of PNG (Foale, 2005: 19-20; Feary *et al.*, 2010), in Vanuatu (Hickey, 2006; Calandra, 2017: 208-219), in the Solomon Islands (Foale *et al.*, 2011), in New Caledonia (Leblic, 1989: 112-114, 2008: 225, 233-237; Leblic and Cornier, 2018: 133), in Fiji (Nolet, 2018; Fache, 2020), or quite largely around Polynesia under the name *rahui* (Bambridge, 2016). In the *Vala North* film, an inhabitant of the Lavongai village of Saula, Jimmy Natgai, says the meaning of the word *vala* is ‘respect’.

When the NGO uses the term *vala* to refer to a type of ‘marine protected area’, it is therefore clearly aiming to combine local practices and scientific considerations. On the one hand, from local practices, the NGO is using the word itself, the marker that signals that a place should be avoided, as well as the ritual or even ‘supernatural’ efficacy of the practice. Indeed, for Ailan Awareness, the *vala* is explicitly tied to a collection of representations that are part of the non-Christian magical or religious field. The supernatural beings that lend their strength to the *vala*, the *anit*, guard these areas, and anyone who disrespects them would risk becoming sick, or even dying, ‘poisoned’ or ‘bewitched’. Finally, the NGO also relies on the idea of respect that is associated with the practice. On the other hand, from the scientific considerations, it includes justifications and rationalisations based on ecosystem analysis and knowledge of reef biology. Therefore, the NGO is clearly attempting to adapt local knowledge to exogenous goals. Friction ensues between these various considerations, creating a new ensemble of knowledge, a new *vala*.

There remain for the NGO two major issues when attempting to encourage the creation of such *vala*: it must be determined who has authority over a given area; then, if a fishing prohibition should be established, this must effectively be enforced. Two crucial factors for understanding the frictions between points of view on marine life on Lavongai therefore emerge: marine tenure, and sociopolitical organisation.

Who do reefs belong to, and who can prohibit fishing?

PNG’s legal system states that land tenure is governed by each social group, locally, according to their own ‘customs’ or ‘traditional’ ways. On the island of Lavongai, twelve matrilineal *patmani* (*klen* in Tok Pisin, i.e. clans) are distinguished, one of which is said to be extinct: Uk. They are associated with twelve birds that they are named after. On land that is claimed by one’s own clan, anybody can build a house or clear a patch of forest in order to start a garden. Nevertheless, it is also possible for a man (but not a woman) to make a ceremonial payment to another clan than his own, in order to secure usage rights over a piece of land. He may even transfer these rights to a son, as long as payment is renewed by him. Land tenure is therefore a rather dynamic affair.

Coastal marine areas are considered to be under the purview of whichever clan owns the neighbouring piece of land, and are sometimes considered the property of all inhabitants of a coastal community. However, according to anthropologist Ton Otto¹⁸, on Lavongai, beyond a few hundred metres from the shore, the notion of ‘tenure’ no longer has meaning (1998: 149), as is the case in Oceania in general (Teulières-Preston, 2000: 130-131). Between houses, boundaries are marked by cordylines and other plants, and in garden areas, there are earth mounds. At sea, limits between various areas are harder to pinpoint. Only development of various lucrative marine activities have

17 This is the terminology from the page on the website of the United Nations Program for Development that introduces the film (<https://perma.cc/6HDR-4UCT>).

18 Ton Otto was in the area in 1989 to study marine tenure in the Tungak and Tigak linguistic area (on Lavongai and adjacent islands, see MAP 2), for the Department of Fisheries and Marine Resources of PNG.

prompted people to determine very precise limits in some places (Otto, 1998: 245-246), this is particularly the case with the harvesting of sea cucumbers (*Holothuroidea*)¹⁹.

In practice, it is rare for a person to be prevented from accessing the ocean in order to carry out subsistence fishing on Lavongai, and commercial fisheries are rare around the island. Since everybody can therefore fish almost anywhere, and since tenure is flexible and involves all the members of a clan on a local level, setting up a system of marine protected areas appears to be a complex undertaking. Such observations have repeatedly been made in Western Oceania (see Hviding, 1998; Foale and Macintyre, 2000; Leblic and Cornier, 2018).

Creation of such areas is met with various reactions on the part of inhabitants. For example, in the village of Lavongai (which gave its name to the island), on the south coast, an area of fishing prohibition, called *vala*, has been set up by Ailan Awareness members for several years now. According to John Aini, who is from this village (an important fact), inhabitants respect the prohibition, rarely fish in the area, and there are apparently already positive spill-over effects (see Lorenzo *et al.*, 2020), bringing an abundance of fish to nearby areas. On the contrary, in the similar area that I was told had been set up for several years in Metevoe by a man from the village who was described as not very respected, people continued to fish regularly in 2019, although some did say they no longer used deris root in this section (which in any case, has long been banned nationally, see note 13). This comparison brings up issues of individual authority, and political power.

Part of the work of WCS is to identify people on the island that the NGO believes will be able to enact management decisions regarding marine areas; who will, in particular, be able to set up and get people to respect prohibition areas. Such people must have enough legitimacy, at least at the village level, for their injunctions to have consequences. Various institutions grant positions of power on Lavongai. On the one hand, national regulations define a considerable number: village piloting council, village courts, wards, development committees (to list but a few). On the other hand, three local institutions²⁰, which the Lavongai themselves group under the name *ri vap lava* (literally ‘the big men’), allow a number of men to acquire a measure of non-hereditary power, which is constantly put into play and challenged. This is not the case for women, who are excluded from the roles of *vap lava*, are very rarely elected, and hold—with few exceptions only—very little power²¹. However ‘big’ these men might be, they have variable and usually scant authority. Their ability to accumulate power is in fact limited by a complex set of obligations that tie them to those who have participated in increasing their prestige by providing help or gifts, and they must—periodically—pay back such gifts and help, decreasing their own abilities in the process. Nevertheless, it is mainly by the prestige afforded them by such institutions that some men manage to enact rules that others will respect.

19 The export of sea cucumber was forbidden in PNG by a 2009 moratorium, put in place because high levels of over-exploitation were being observed. This was lifted for a short period in 2017, and the quotas that had been determined at this time were very rapidly exceeded, by over 80%, and it has been in place ever since (see Hair *et al.*, 2018, 2020).

20 These are the *pasingan*, charismatic speakers, who forge their position of power through ritual distributions of valuables such as pig, taro, *inangun* (*mias* in Tok Pisin, a currency made from threaded fragments of shells); the *vaitas*, last stage initiates of a secret society; and the *vosap*, war chiefs. These three figures are reminiscent of the ‘big man’ (Sahlins, 1963; Lindstrom, 1981; Clay, 1992) and ‘great man’ (Godelier, 1990; Godelier and Strathern, 1991) found in almost every society in the region, but a more detailed presentation of their specificities would be out of place here.

21 Such gender inequality is widespread, profound and marked in PNG and in the region, where several NGOs are attempting to address the issue (see for example the « Pacific Women in Politics » website, in particular the PNG page: <https://perma.cc/D68L-PDEW>). Research has shown there are close ties between such gender inequalities, levels of education, economic development, and modes of management of natural resources (see Foale, 2008; Mangubhai and Lawless, 2021).

What moral, intellectual and ideological justifications does Ailan Awareness use in order to convince people that restrictive or prohibitive measures regarding fishing should be applied? John Aini says his work relies on what in Tok Pisin is known as *kastom*. This word, which literally means ‘custom’, ‘tradition’ or ‘ancestral practice’, refers in Western Oceania to ‘positive aspects of post-colonial collective identification’ (Tabani, 2013: 18-19, own translation), and has been the topic of extensive anthropological publication (see in particular: Keesing, 1982; Jolly and Thomas, 1992; Abong and Tabani, 2013; McDonnell *et al.*, 2017). In this context, referring to *kastom* is a way to give both efficacy and legitimacy to marine management practices. John Aini considered that *kastom* has always contained principles that are virtuous for marine conservation. He mentions *vala* as a practical example of one such principle.

He also describes the *polepole*, ‘a traditional fish aggregating device’ (Aini and West, 2013: 2), as having virtues in the context of marine resource management. Nowadays, such *polepole* have become rare, and John Aini encourages the islands inhabitants to build them again. These are well known of the Lavongai people, since the drawing below, representing a *polepole* (DRAWING 1), was produced spontaneously by Gregory Ravis in my absence, in order to explain to me how one worked. According to him, and other interlocutors in Metevoe, the *polepole* is a fish trap, formed by creating a wall out of coral stones in a semi-circle around a *neilik*, a pool of water that is isolated at low tide. It is used by opening it at rising tide, in order to let in the fish, and by closing it as the tide goes down. Its use must be preceded by ritual work in order to ensure its efficacy²².

22 Such traps exist or have existed in the past in various locations on New Caledonia (Leblic, 2008: 72-74), as well as in Polynesia, for example on Tokelau, where they are called *fota* (Ono, 2010: 9) or in the Tuamotu, where they are called *kaua paru* (Torrente, 2015: 22) and no doubt on many other Oceanian coasts.

DRAWING 1
 -
 Drawing of the La-vongai coast showing a polepole: a stone fish trap, built using a ngoto (pile of stones). Neirina refers to the village; ngerelo the beach or coast; kulikasung the intertidal area (kasung is a marine plant that grows there); neikalat refers

to the part of the reef flat that doesn't dry, even at low tide; nailik is a pool of water isolated on the reef flat at low tide; takaman refers to the traps door; dong at to the stones that are set aside in order to close it; kuliliung is the reef drop-off.

By Gregory Ravis, approx. 60 year old man, Metevoe, 12/11/2019. Reproduced with his kind permission.

From Ailan Awareness' perspective, how is the use of such a trap able to help manage fish stocks? If I understand correctly, it is for their collective and customary qualities that the polepole are considered virtuous. Acceptability of fishing restrictions rests for the NGO on these two aspects

of their activities: the collective, and the customary. It is therefore because it demonstrates those two qualities that the *polepole* represents a form of ‘good management’ with regard to marine life. No longer really a trap, nor a ‘management tool’ in the sense in which a marine ecologist might use the term, this is therefore, once again, a hybrid object, just as the *vala* is.

Ailan Awareness’ goal—durable management of marine areas—creates friction as it comes into contact with dynamic local political institutions and tenure systems. These frictions force actors within the NGO, and inhabitants of the island, to recompose their knowledge, and to give new value to extant or nearly forgotten knowledge (*vala* and *polepole*), and to devalue others, as we will see in the next part of this text. This is concerned with a third point of friction, the subject of which is the motivations that various actors have in preserving marine life, as well as their respective ‘world-views’ and specific objectives.

One objectives, several worldviews?

Although the Lavongai, Ailan Awareness and WCS are in appearance unanimous regarding the need for durable management of marine life, the justifications that are employed in this respect by each set of actors are divergent. The data presented above shows how, for the Lavongai, the notion of respect is central to the relations with these living beings, and that Ailan Awareness grounds their action in *kastom* and a form of collective organisation of resource management. What about WCS?

The international NGO justifies their action in this region by what is referred to as the ‘pristine’ state of the marine ecosystem (WCS, 2018). Lavongai is indeed on the outer reach of the ‘coral triangle’ (Hoeksema, 2007) and the reefs around the island are highly biodiverse. Nevertheless, human populations have been interacting with marine species in the Bismarck Archipelago for at least 35 millennia (Allen et Kershaw, 1996: 185); on Lavongai, where only few archaeological digs have been carried out, some traces suggest human occupation up to 4,000 years ago (Leavesley and Troitzsch, 2007: 253). In a document that was handed out during one of their training sessions, WCS lists what are considered to be ‘threats to marine resources’ in the area surrounding Kavieng, first of which is ‘population increase’²³. In the NGO’s perspective, a relatively sparse population has, during the last few centuries, allowed the reefs to remain in a ‘pristine’ state. However, the current increase in human population, still according to WCS, could cause ‘malthusian overfishing’ (McClanahan *et al.*, 2008): an increase in fishing efforts proportional to the number of mouths to feed. On the neighbouring island of New Ireland, biologists working for the NGO have measured such effects near Kavieng, and state that some fish species are already overfished (Frijlink, 2017; Booth *et al.*, 2019).

However, the potential for overfishing on the part of a still very sparse Lavongai population, of barely 66 inhabitants per kilometre of coast²⁴, should be compared with the impact of international industrialised fishing, which is already having devastating and well documented effects on the ocean’s fauna (Díaz *et al.*, 2019: 1617, § 12). The risk here—well identified by Simon Foale, Michelle Dyer and Jeff Kinch—is that interactions with the international NGO should turn into one more injunction to austerity for a population that is already living in some of the most precarious conditions in the world (Foale *et al.*, 2016: 27). The three authors stress how mankind’s bioclimatic

23 According to the 2000 and 2010 census (UNOCHA and PNG NSO, 2012), the number of inhabitants on Lavongai is indeed increasing at an annual rate of approx. 3 %, which is comparable to the rest of the country, and, worldwide, would be considered high.

24 The Lavongai coast can be measured to be approx. 450 km long (estimated in QGIS using OpenStreetMaps data available on <https://osmdata.openstreetmap.de/data/coastlines.html>). For 30 000 inhabitants, the ratio of 66 inhab./km is obtained, which is identical to the Solomon Islands, for example, and very low, compared to countries with a similar coastline length to surface area ration (around 300 m/km²): 21 269 in Singapore, 784 in Bahrain, or 5 882 in Sao Tomé-and-Principe.

imprint is largely caused by ‘developed’ nations, and point out the paradox inherent in the fact that NGO’s from these very nations are recommending adaptations to PNG’s inhabitants, when the country is 155th out of 189 on the Human Development Index scale (Foale *et al.*, 2016: 25).

On Lavongai island, WCS focus their work on creating awareness, by giving advice and training to villagers, actions their official writings (see for example WCS, 2020), refer to by expressions such as ‘empowerment’ or ‘capacity building’ (about the use of such buzzwords in international NGO’s vocabulary, see Cornwall and Brock, 2005). When the inhabitants of Metevoe expressed themselves during the joint Ailan Awareness and WCS training sessions I observed, they were already largely aware of the risks of overfishing, and of the dangers that techniques such as fishing with deris root represent (no doubt thanks to the efforts of these two NGOs). Nevertheless, although deris root is by and large recognized as being detrimental to marine life on Lavongai, it is still frequently used. John Aini states on this matter that fishing with deris root is one of the techniques that requires the least knowledge about marine life (Aini and West, 2013: 3), and it is used above all by children, even though the whole population will enjoy its products, and adult men and women also use it. We therefore see the Lavongai are devaluing some of their fishing knowledge: that which relates to ichthyotoxic plants. This process is still ongoing, as is evidenced by the gap between statements and practices on this matter.

The Lavongai also formulate explicit and specific demands towards WCS, an organization they perceive as powerful and rich. For example, they wish to obtain fishing equipment, or the installation of anchored coastal fish aggregating devices. In the past, such installations have been set up by Ailan Awareness, then WCS in the area (Frijlink, 2017: 63) and their apparent efficacy is seen by the Lavongai as a possible way to compensate for the added difficulty, or even impossibility in obtaining fish that a prohibition on a reef area would bring about. The Lavongai perspective is therefore as follows: if they should ‘make concessions’ by not fishing in a protected area, or by not using deris root, then WCS should ‘give something back’ in a way, in a spirit of reciprocity and exchange²⁵.

Faced with such concrete requests, WCS does show signs of wanting to adapt their own knowledge by questioning their practices. In an article she published in *Pacific Conservation Biology*, the biologist that is at the head of the Melanesian branch of WCS, Stacy Jupiter (2017), lists various difficulties NGOs such as WCS, that work in the field of marine conservation, have been faced with in the region. She too refers to the issue of land tenure and political organisation, but goes even further, stating that:

‘Melanesian world-views on nature and conservation differ from some prevailing western perspectives in ways that affect how Melanesians and outsiders interact with nature, what types of responsibilities they assume, and the types of conservation actions and management systems that they independently design (Keppel *et al.* 2012a). One major difference is the Melanesian perception of humans as part of nature versus western views of people apart from nature, termed the nature-culture dualism (Descola and Pálsson 1996; Haila 2000).’ (Jupiter, 2017: 139)

‘Anthropology of nature’ (Descola, 2001), which Stacy Jupiter is referring to here, has indeed shown how the categories of ‘nature’ and ‘culture’ are relative, and that ontologies that consider both as separate are socially grounded in a certain context (the one she calls ‘western’, see Latour, 1991; Ingold, 2000; Descola, 2005; Viveiros de Castro, 2012). However, considering WCS’s objectives, the issue for the NGO should be less about whether the Lavongai distinguish anything that might be called ‘nature’²⁶, nor—if they do—whether they considered themselves to be part of it or

25 Anchored fish aggregating device (FAD) are created by mooring a floating object (made of wood, steel or plastic) to the seafloor. Marine flora then settles quickly under the device, which leads to the development of a whole ecosystem. Fish then approach to consume the plants and fauna that are near the FAD. It is then possible to go near the device in order to catch fish, by using a vessel such as a canoe.

26 Such a question is a major focus of my currently ongoing doctoral research.

not. Their ‘world-view’ clearly doesn’t preclude attaching value to the preservation of the ‘wildlife’ WCS is aiming to ‘conserve’. Moreover, building interactions with their environment that are both long lasting for the humans and non-humans involved is an objective all share on the island. The divergence that appears between the inhabitants statements and the NGO’s relate to the reasons for which such and objective should be sought. Where WCS talk of the ‘pristine’ qualities of these reefs—that have been inhabited for generations—and consider that the population needs to be ‘made aware’ of the dangers it faces in order to preserve existing biodiversity, the Lavongai refer to the respect owed to living beings, and are preoccupied far more by social, economic, and subsistence issues.

Conclusion

The bodies of knowledge that different groups of actors hold when meeting during environmental NGOs actions are not, *a priori*, ‘compatible’ with each other, and therefore such meetings cause ‘friction’. On Lavongai, I have shown how such circumstances cause the people involved to reshape their knowledge. On the one hand, the inhabitants of the island alongside members of Ailan Awareness build new, recomposed institutions such as the modern versions of *vala* and *polepole*. On the other hand, the same inhabitants revalue some of their own knowledge—such as the notion of ‘respect’ owed to living beings—devalue others—fishing with deris root—and are prepared to integrate into their technical repertoire new possibilities from foreign sources—such as FADs. Finally, the ecologists working for WCS question the foundations of their own way of giving value to and preserving living beings in contexts such as Lavongai, where land tenure, sociopolitical organisation and the inhabitant’s preoccupations appear to be at cross purposes with the international NGO’s actions.

Because they are concerned with living beings, these forms of recomposed and revalued knowledge are ‘collaboratively agreed upon Natural objects’ (Tsing, 2005: 89). They are hybrid forms of knowledge, that question dualisms such as nature-culture, modern-traditional, human-non-human, local-global. Here, anthropology’s ‘post-humanist approach’ (Descola, 2014: 268) may therefore find important loci for the observation and analysis of current evolutions in mankind’s relation with our environment. One of the most fruitful avenues for such an anthropology might be to follow Bruno Latour’s invitation to ‘welcome such hybrids and give them a place, a name, a house, a philosophy, an ontology’ (Latour, 1991: 42).

Thanks

I wish to address my most sincere thanks to the people who’s guest I was in Metevoe, for their help, their friendship, and their fraternity: *kalaro luai* Laimen, Teresia, Melis, Lumaias, Gregori, William, James and all the others. Thank you also to John Aini and Paige West for their help, for allowing me to stay in Kaselok, and for their reading of this article and comments before publication. Thank you to all the members of Ailan Awareness and to the employees of the Kavieng branch of WCS. Thank you to Adrian Berenson, Pascale Bonnemère, Anne Di Piazza, Juliette Pesce and Piera Simon-Chaix for their comments and corrections on early versions of this article. Thank you to the editorial committee of the *Journal de la Société des Océanistes*, to Céline Travési, the editor of this special section, to the two anonymous reviewers for their rigorous and constructive criticism.

Filmography

GORDON Stephani, 2019, *Vala North*, short film (12 minutes), production David Mitchell, photography Stephani Gordon, writing and editing Dan Evans, produced by Open Boat Films,

with the collaboration of Ailan Awareness and Eco Custodian Advocates, with the support of the Small Grants Programme of the Global Environment Facility, under the United Nations Development Program (<https://archive.org/details/vala-north-hh-szkn-u-3z-a>).

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